

Service Recommendation System Using Machine Learning

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Abstract—In the rapidly evolving on-demand service ecosystem, users often face difficulty in selecting the most suitable service provider due to the availability of numerous options. Traditional systems provide generic listings without personalization, leading to inefficient decision-making. This study proposes a Machine Learning-based Service Recommendation System that suggests optimal service providers based on user preferences, location, ratings, past booking history, and real-time availability. The system employs similarity-based techniques such as Cosine Similarity and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) to analyze relationships between users and services. By transforming user interactions into numerical feature vectors, the model computes similarity scores and ranks service providers accordingly. The system further enhances recommendation accuracy by incorporating contextual features and dynamic updates.

The proposed approach improves user satisfaction and platform efficiency by delivering personalized and data-driven recommendations. The study also discusses implementation strategies, challenges, and future enhancements for scalable intelligent systems.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Recommendation System, Cosine Similarity, KNN, Personalization

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid growth of digital platforms and mobile applications has significantly increased the availability of on-demand services such as home maintenance, transportation, personal assistance, and healthcare. While this expansion has improved accessibility, it has also introduced challenges for users in selecting the most suitable service provider from a large pool of available options.

Conventional service platforms typically present service providers based on basic filtering criteria such as ratings, distance, or popularity. However, these approaches fail to capture individual user preferences, behavioral patterns, and contextual factors. As a result, users often spend considerable time searching for services and may still end up making suboptimal decisions.

To address this issue, recommendation systems have emerged as an effective solution for providing personalized service suggestions. By leveraging machine learning techniques, these systems analyze historical data, user interactions, and service attributes to identify patterns and predict user

preferences. This enables the system to recommend services that are more relevant and tailored to individual needs.

Among various machine learning approaches, similarity-based techniques such as Cosine Similarity and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) are widely used due to their simplicity and effectiveness. These methods compare users and services based on feature representations and identify the most relevant matches for recommendation.

In addition to personalization, modern recommendation systems also incorporate contextual factors such as location, time, and service availability. Considering these factors enhances the practicality and relevance of recommendations, particularly in real-world service environments.

This study proposes a Machine Learning-based Service Recommendation System that integrates user preferences, service characteristics, and contextual information to generate accurate and personalized recommendations. The system aims to improve user experience, reduce decision-making effort, and enhance the efficiency of service platforms by delivering intelligent, data-driven suggestions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recommendation systems have been widely studied in the fields of machine learning and data mining, with applications in e-commerce, entertainment, and service-based platforms. Various techniques have been developed to improve recommendation accuracy, personalization, and scalability.

One of the most widely used approaches is Collaborative Filtering (CF), which generates recommendations based on the preferences and behavior of similar users or items. In user-based collaborative filtering, recommendations are made by identifying users with similar interests, whereas item-based collaborative filtering focuses on the similarity between items or services. Sarwar et al. proposed item-based collaborative filtering, which is more scalable and efficient than user-based approaches, as it computes similarity between items using measures such as cosine similarity.

Similarity measures play a crucial role in recommendation systems. Among them, cosine similarity is widely used due to its effectiveness in handling high-dimensional data. It measures the angle between two vectors representing users or

items, allowing the system to determine their degree of similarity. This method is particularly useful for sparse datasets, which are common in real-world applications.

Another important technique is the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm, which identifies the top k similar users or items based on similarity scores. KNN is simple, intuitive, and effective for recommendation tasks. However, it suffers from high computational cost and reduced performance when applied to large-scale datasets.

Despite their effectiveness, traditional collaborative filtering methods face several limitations, including the cold start problem, where new users or items lack sufficient data for generating recommendations, and data sparsity, where user-item interaction matrices contain many missing values. These challenges reduce the accuracy and reliability of recommendations.

To overcome these limitations, researchers have proposed hybrid recommendation systems that combine collaborative filtering with content-based approaches. These systems utilize both user behavior and item attributes to improve recommendation quality. Additionally, context-aware recommendation systems have been introduced, incorporating factors such as location, time, and user context to enhance relevance.

Recent advancements in machine learning have led to the development of deep learning-based recommendation systems, which can model complex user-item interactions and capture hidden patterns in large datasets. Although these methods provide high accuracy, they require significant computational resources and large volumes of data.

In the context of service recommendation systems, incorporating real-time factors such as service availability, geographic proximity, and user preferences is essential for practical applications. However, many existing systems still rely heavily on static data and do not fully utilize contextual information. This study builds upon traditional similarity-based approaches by integrating cosine similarity and KNN with additional contextual features such as location, ratings, and availability. The proposed system aims to overcome the limitations of existing methods by providing more accurate, personalized, and real-time service recommendations.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system suggested is a Service Recommendation System that is based on Machine Learning and is capable of giving personalized, accurate, and context-aware service recommendations to users. The system combines the behavior, service attributes, and contextual information of the user to break the constraints of the conventional recommendation methods.

The proposed system unlike the traditional systems which depend on the rating or popularity alone, focuses on several aspects including the preferences and the location of users, the booking history, rating of the service and the real time availability. The system can be used to produce very relevant recommendations by combining those features with other machine learning techniques based on similarity.

A. System Architecture

The proposed system architecture is composed of multiple interconnected modules that collaboratively generate efficient and personalized service recommendations. Each module performs a specific function, contributing to the overall performance of the system.

- 1) *User Profile Module*: The user profile module is responsible for managing and storing user-specific information. It captures essential details such as:
 - User preferences
 - Location information
 - Previous booking records
 - Ratings and feedback

This information helps in understanding user behavior and enables personalized recommendations.

- 2) *Service Provider Database*: This module maintains comprehensive information about service providers. The stored details include:
 - Service categories
 - Ratings and customer reviews
 - Geographic location
 - Availability status

The database is continuously updated to reflect real-time service conditions.

- 3) *Data Preprocessing Module*: The collected data is pre-processed to improve data quality and consistency. This involves:
 - Handling missing and inconsistent values
 - Normalizing numerical data
 - Encoding categorical attributes

This step ensures that the data is suitable for further machine learning operations.

- 4) *Feature Engineering Module*: In this stage, important features are extracted and transformed into numerical representations. Key features include:
 - User preference score
 - Distance between user and service provider
 - Average service rating
 - Booking frequency
 - Service popularity

These features represent both user behavior and service characteristics in vector form.

- 5) *Similarity Computation Module*: The system computes similarity between users and service providers using cosine similarity. Each entity is represented as a feature vector, and similarity is calculated as:

$$\text{Similarity}(A, B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \times \|B\|} \quad (1)$$

This helps in identifying services that closely match user preferences.

Fig. 1. Service Recommendation System Architecture

6) *Recommendation Engine (KNN-Based)*: The recommendation engine uses the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm to select the most relevant service providers. It performs the following steps:

- Selects top k similar services
- Ranks and item Filters the results

This ensures accurate, relevant, and efficient recommendation generation.

B. Machine Learning Pipeline

The suggested system is based on a machine learning pipeline that has a structured flow of processing raw data and producing meaningful recommendations on the services. First, information is gathered on several platforms such as users profiles, details of service providers, and previous booking history. Preprocessing of the collected data involves missing values, numerical feature normalization, and codifying categorical variables, among other things, to provide consistency and usability.

Following the preprocessing, pertinent features like the user choices, distance between the user and the service provider,

mean users rating and the frequency of booking are obtained and converted to numerical feature vectors. These vectors are then used to calculate scores of similarity based on the cosine similarity, the measure of the similarity between users and service providers.

Using these similarity scores, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is used to find the top k most useful service providers. The services chosen are then ranked and filtered based on real time factors including constraints and availability. Lastly, the system will produce and display a list of suggested recommendations of personalized services to the user and guarantee greater accuracy, relevance, and user satisfaction.

C. System Workflow

The system workflow is a step-by-step procedure of how the suggested recommendation system based on the service proposal creates individual recommendations. First, the user is taken into the system and gives a service request and the inputs which are required like preferences and location. Employing this input the system pulls out the data related to the service provider(s) in the database. The data obtained is further preprocessed and converted into organized feature vectors that incorporate the preferences of users and service features.

The system then calculates similarity scores on the user and the service providers which are available based on cosine similarity. The algorithm of K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) utilizes these values of similarity to determine the most relevant service providers. A ranking of the chosen services is then achieved based on similarity rates and sorted based on real-time aspects like availability and constraints. Lastly, the system produces a list of best recommended service providers and shows them to the user via interfaces thereby making sure that service is selected correctly, personalized and efficiently.

IV. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The quality of the dataset that will be used is one of the key factors that will determine the performance of the proposed Service Recommendation System. The data set is the relationship between the users and the service providers and appropriate contextual and behavioral features in order to come up with accurate recommendations.

The data will be in the form of structured information obtained through activities of users and profiles of service providers. It also contains user ID, service provider ID, service category, ratings, geographic location (latitude and longitude), booking history and the availability of the service. The following attributes are useful in the modeling of user preferences, as well as service characteristics, which are necessary to the personalized recommendation.

In the phase of preparing the dataset, there are several sources of raw data, which include contact with users, records of booking, databases about service providers. The received evidence is then preprocessed to eliminate discrepancies, deal with null values and eliminate duplicates. Numerical values

Fig. 2. Dataset Structure and User-Service Interaction Matrix

are made normalized so that they become homogeneous and categorical variables like types of services are converted into numerical measures of the service so that it can be fed into machine learning.

The engineering of the feature is carried out to obtain meaningful features including user preference score, distance between user and service provider, average provider rating, and the frequency of booking. These features are converted to the numerical feature vectors of both the users and services in a multiplexing space.

Lastly, the data is arranged as a user-service interaction matrix with the row as the users and the column as the service providers with the values being ratings or interaction scores. Such structured representation allows effective similarity calculation and recommendation generation by means of cosine similarity and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithms.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed Service Recommendation System is developed as a web-based application that combines machine learning techniques with an interactive user interface to provide personalized service suggestions. The implementation emphasizes efficient data handling, precise similarity calculations, and smooth coordination between different system modules.

Python is used as the core programming language, supported by libraries such as Pandas and NumPy for data processing and preprocessing tasks, and Scikit-learn for implementing machine learning algorithms. The frontend interface is built using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, while the backend is developed using frameworks like Flask or Django to manage application logic and ensure communication between components. A MySQL database is employed to store user data, service provider information, and booking records.

The process begins at the user interface, where users can create accounts, log in, and submit service requests by pro-

viding inputs such as location and preferences. These inputs are forwarded to the backend, where the data management module retrieves the necessary information from the database. The retrieved data is then preprocessed through cleaning, normalization, and encoding techniques to prepare it for machine learning operations.

Following preprocessing, feature engineering is carried out to extract significant attributes such as user preference scores, service ratings, distance between the user and service provider, and booking frequency. These attributes are transformed into numerical feature vectors, which are used for further analysis. To determine similarity, the cosine similarity algorithm is applied to compare user vectors with service provider vectors. Based on the computed similarity scores, the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is used to identify the top k most relevant service providers. These selected services are then ordered according to similarity values and refined by considering real-time factors such as availability.

The final set of recommendations is returned to the frontend and presented to the user in a structured format, including service ratings, provider details, and availability information. The system ensures efficient interaction between frontend, backend, and database components, enabling real-time recommendation delivery.

Furthermore, the system is designed to be scalable, allowing it to accommodate increasing volumes of user data and service providers. Performance can be further enhanced by incorporating optimization techniques such as efficient data structures and caching strategies for large-scale deployment.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed Service Recommendation System is tested on the basis of the capability to offer accurate, relevant, and personalized service recommendations. A dataset of user profiles, service provider details and past booking records was used to test the system.

The cosine similarity and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) make up the recommendation model that was able to productively identify similar users and service providers leading to meaningful and contextually relevant recommendations. The system was tested to suit the various preference of the users and dynamically create suggestions to real time input like location and availability.

Precision and recall are some of the metrics used in evaluating the accuracy of the recommendations. The system was very precise meaning that the recommended services were applicable to the preferences of the user. Also, it was noted that the value of the recall was high to the extent that the system could retrieve a large fraction of appropriate service providers in the dataset.

The quality of recommendations was also enhanced due to the inclusion of the contextual characteristics of the area of geographic location and availability of services. The suggestions to the users were not only similar to their tastes, but also accessible and available at the necessary time in a practical way.

The user interface was created in a manner that would be easy to use such that the user could easily view and chose suggested services. The system was efficient in its response time and this shows that the system has the capability of producing real-time recommendations.

The system however has some limitations. There can be the reduction of performance when the only limited user data is encountered (cold start problem), and the computational cost of similarity computations can grow with larger datasets. The suggested system offers a scalable and reliable solution to service recommendation on a personal basis in spite of these difficulties.

All in all, the findings show that when machine learning methods are incorporated with contextual information, the effectiveness and usefulness of service recommendation systems increase substantially.

VII. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Despite the fact that the proposed Service Recommendation System offers personalized and context-based recommendation, its performance and applicability to the real world are impacted by a number of challenges and limitations.

The cold start problem is one of the main issues as it happens when new users or new service providers are introduced into the system without enough historical data. The model of recommendation heavily depends on the historical interactions between the user and the host, including ratings and the booking history, therefore, it is hard to provide proper recommendations at the initial stages when this information is not available.

This is another critical problem as it is called data sparsity, in which the number of service providers that the user interacts with is minimal to the number of available services. This causes a low user-service interaction matrix which diminishes the performance of similarity-based methods like cosine similarity and KNN and makes the recommendations less reliable. The quality of input data is also very crucial to the system. False ratings, missing values, biasness, and inconsistency in records may adversely affect the performance of the model. Low quality data may also result in inaccurate similarity computations and eventually cause poor accuracy in the recommendations. Another significant issue is scalability. The computational cost of similarity calculations and neighbor selection increases with the size of the number of users and providers of the service. This may lead to reduced response times and more resources consumed particularly in a large scale system.

Moreover, the system is not as flexible in real time. Even though it takes the availability into account, it might not reflect quickly evolving conditions like the sudden change in demand, dynamic pricing, or immediate changes in the service status. This may have an impact on the timeliness and relevance of suggestions.

The system can also be over-specialized whereby recommendations are mainly based on the previous behavior of a user thus reducing the possibility of knowing new services or

a variety of services. This diminishes the discovery nature of recommendation systems.

Lastly, there are privacy and security issues because of the sensitive user data that can be accessed like location, preferences and booking history. To deploy it in reality, it is critical to guarantee the safety of the data storage, the access control, and privacy-enabling mechanisms.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

The proposed Service Recommendation System offers efficient and individualized recommendations; nonetheless, there are a number of opportunities that can be utilized to enhance it further in order to achieve better performances, scalability, and practicality in the real world.

The future work on the topic includes one of the directions that include implementing the more advanced machine learning models like deep learning and matrix factorization models. Such methods are able to model complex and non-linear user service relationships, hence enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of the recommendations in large-scale settings.

The other important enhancement is the creation of real time recommendation system. Subsequently, through the integration of streaming data and real-time updates, the system will dynamically respond to the changes in user behavior, service availability, and demand trends to make sure that the recommendations are also up-to-date and relevant.

Another upgrade to the system is to include a user feedback mechanism where the user-interactions in the form of clicks, ratings and reviews are constantly gathered and used to optimize the recommendation model. This allows learning to be adaptive and enhances personalization in long-term.

The further development of work can be aimed at enhancing the usefulness of the context-based suggestions by incorporating new contextual variables like time of the day, activity patterns of the user, seasonal patterns, and dynamical pricing. This will allow the system to offer better and situation aware suggestions.

Scalability issues can be resolved by building the system to support cloud computing and distributed computing platforms to enable large amounts of data to be processed in order to support more and more users and service providers.

A mobile-based application is also another possible improvement that will contribute to ease of access and allow users to get real-time notifications and recommendations without issues.

Lastly, further studies can be made on how to improve the privacy and security of data through application of encryption method, secure authentication process, and privacy-sensitive models of recommendation to guarantee the secure manipulation of sensitive user data.

IX. CONCLUSION

The offered Service Recommendation System proves successful in terms of the implementation of machine learning methods in resolving the issues related to the choice of the

appropriate service provider within the contemporary problems of the on-demand platform. With the aid of similarity-based computing algorithms (Cosine Similarity and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)) the system can create its own personalized and relevant recommendations on the basis of user behavior and service attributes.

The system also has several options, such as user preferences, ratings of services, location, booking history, and real time availability, thus making the recommendations much accurate and relevant. Raw data is processed into the structured forms that facilitate computation of similarities and ranking of service providers effectively by performing data preprocessing and feature engineering.

The web-based nature of the system makes it practical and easy to use by the user and also guarantees smooth interaction between the user and the recommendation engine. The combination of machine learning tools and actual service data shows the possibilities of intelligent systems in enhancing user engagement and informative decision-making.

In general, the suggested system is an efficient and scalable approach in terms of customized service ranking. It shows how properly-organized data and suitable machine learning algorithms can be jointly used to create smart and user-friendly systems, which can provide accurate, context-sensitive, and meaningful recommendations in practice.

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